

First record of *Gambierdiscus* cf. *australes* in Iberian Coastal Waters (western Mediterranean Sea)

Species of the genus *Gambierdiscus* R. Adachi & Y. Fukuyo (Dinophyta, Gonyaulacales) are known for their ability to produce potent polyether toxins, ciguatoxins and maitotoxins, which are responsible for ciguatera, the most prevalent and severe non-bacterial foodborne illness worldwide [1]. This syndrome arises from consumption of fish that have bioaccumulated toxins through the food web, causing gastrointestinal, neurological and sometimes cardiovascular symptoms. Ciguatera poses a major public health concern in affected areas, with an estimated incidence of 50,000 cases annually (although this figure may be underes-

timated [2]), alongside significant economic impacts on fisheries, seafood trade, and tourism [3].

Although originally considered strictly circumtropical, *Gambierdiscus* species have recently been reported in temperate waters, including the Mediterranean Sea (Greece, Cyprus, Balearic Islands) [4, 5]. Here, we report the first detection of *Gambierdiscus* cf. *australes* on the north coast of Alicante province (Spain), making this the first record of the genus on the continental coasts of the western Mediterranean basin. Molecular analyses are currently being conducted on this material to determine the specific status of *Gambierdis-*

cus cf. *australes* in Iberian coastal waters, aiming for full confirmation of its taxonomic identity.

In this study, two sampling campaigns were carried out in March and September 2023 in six zones (Racons, Marines, Reserva, Antonio, Arenal and Portitxol) along the Dénia-Jávea coast (Fig. 1), with a total of 12 sampling points (Fig. 2). Points designated as "S" were located 250 m from the coastline (depth: 5–15 m), and those labelled "P" were 1 km offshore (depth: 8–35 metres). Notably, Reserva S and Antonio S are located within the Marine Reserve of Fisheries Interest of Cabo de San Antonio. The benthic habitats in the area are heterogeneous, predominantly sandy north of the Dénia harbour and rocky to the south, with extensive seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa*) and areas of sciaphilous algae (Fig. 3). At each point, sample bottles collected at the surface and 5 m were mixed (1:1) and a 250 ml aliquot was immediately preserved with acidic Lugol's solution for further analysis. Seawater temperature was measured with a data logger JFE Advantech. While in March only Racons, Marines, Reserva and Antonio were sampled, in September all 12 points were sampled. Cellular abundance was determined according to the Utermöhl method, and species identification was performed via scanning electron microscopy (JEOL JSM-6380LV).

Gambierdiscus cf. *australes* was detected in all samples except Marines S and Antonio S collected in March. Cell concentration ranged from 20 to 140 cells·L⁻¹, with the highest abundances recorded in September (Fig. 4). Seawater temperatures in March and September ranged from 14.9 to 16.3 °C and 26.2 to 27.3 °C, respectively.

Identification of *Gambierdiscus* cf. *australes* (Fig. 5) was based on its lenticular shape, ranging from spherical to ellipsoidal in apical view and dorsoventrally compressed. Measurements included depth (D): 69–77 µm, width (W): 55–74 µm, and length (L): 33–44 µm, with D/W and L/W ratios of 1.14 and 0.6, respectively. The cell surface appeared smooth to slightly rough, with evenly distributed small pores. Plate Po was ellipsoidal, featuring a hook-shaped opening. Plate 2' was rectangular, with suture ratios of 2'1" to 2'3" = 0.69

Fig 1. View of the central area of the Marine Reserve of Fisheries Interest of Cabo de San Antonio (coast of Dénia) from the sampling point Reserva P.

Fig 2. Sampling points in the study area.

and 2'/3' to 2'/1' = 1.53. Plate 2'''' was narrow, pentagonal, and had parallel sides. The morphology and dimensions are consistent with initial descriptions from the Pacific Ocean [6] and subsequent records from other regions [7, 8].

These findings confirm the expansion of the genus *Gambierdiscus* in the Mediterranean Sea, likely facilitated by ocean currents, maritime traffic and the ongoing tropicalization of this sea. *G. cf. australes* demonstrates a high capacity for colonizing new environments beyond its historical range. Although the exact timing of this species' introduction into the coastal waters of the Iberian Peninsula remains unknown, its absence from a recent review of 30 samples collected in May and September 2011 from the same study area, performed by our research group, suggests that its arrival occurred after that year.

The colonization potential of *Gambierdiscus* poses serious challenges, as its presence may remain undetected until toxic events occur. The results obtained underline the urgent need to develop monitoring and control strategies focused on both this genus and the specific communities in which it thrives, to effectively assess the associated risks, mainly to public health and the local economy.

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Fig 3. Seagrass meadows of *Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa* and areas of sciaphilous algae at the study area.

Fig 4. Abundance of *G. australes* at different sampling points. S: shallow points. P: deep points.

Fig 5. SEM Photographs of *G. australes* from the study area. A) Epitheca. B) Hypotheca.

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